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SOME ISSUES OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC GEOGRAPHICAL STUDY OF RURAL AREAS

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Abstract

In this article researching the rural areas is analyzed by means of economical, sociological and ecological spheres and the following issues such as effective using of rural areas and considering the harmonizing system of “nature-population-agriculture” are enlightened in the article.

Keywords: rural areas, the geoecologic-economic condition of the country, degree of geoecologic intensity of rural areas, change in natural landscape composition, demographic pressure, ecologic-economic balance of the region, traditional and innovative branches of the rural economy.

Villages are the product of the interaction, harmony and balance of the "nature-population-economy" system, each of which reflects the natural-landscape, socio-economic characteristics of the area in which they are located. The difference between rural areas and other settlements, such as cities, is that they are more directly related to the area, both in the organization of settlements and in the production process. In Fergana, for example, 42 percent of the population lives in rural areas, while rural areas make up 97 percent of the province's territory. The basis for the

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formation, territorial location and development of villages in Uzbekistan is the culture of the rural population's use of natural resources (primarily land and water).

Today's economic, social and environmental problems in rural areas have been caused by long-term agrarian policy. Efforts to eliminate "unpromising" settlements, to bridge the gap between urban and rural areas, and to stifle rural ownership of property are still having an impact. This is due to the fact that it is difficult to simultaneously implement major reforms in the agricultural sector in rural areas. Until recently, the villages, which were the mainstay of the former economy, were concentrated as a skilled labor force, lacking land resources, employment, and worsening demoeological conditions.

The main part of the population is engaged in agriculture, the amount of anthropogenic impact on the quantitatively limited land and water resources is growing from year to year, the geo-ecological situation is often unfavorable in the use of rural areas of Fergana region Ensuring geo-ecological stability, ie ecological and economic balance, reducing the agro-demographic burden, adapting to the requirements of the landscape on the basis of restoration and enrichment of ethno-ecological culture is an urgent, scientifically-practical task.

The first geographical study of rural areas was carried out by the French scientist P. Georges. The researcher was the first to show that the location of the rural population depends on social and natural factors that affect the conduct of agriculture.

A stratified, specialized approach was used in the geographical study of rural areas (Kochurov B., 1999). Not long after AN Rakitnikov laid the foundations of

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agricultural geography, SA Kovalev developed the theoretical foundations of the geographical study of the rural population. As a result, the geographical study of rural areas was not carried out in close connection with agricultural production. The researchers focused on agriculture or the geography of the rural population. In these studies, there have also been cases of one-sided study of agriculture without the rural population, and rural areas without agriculture, which is the main industry. However, in the early works in the Fergana Valley, a comprehensive approach prevailed (Ahmadaliyev Yu., 2007).

In the field of economic geography, the work done in the Fergana Valley, first of all, shows the problems that will arise in the coming years for the development of agriculture and their solutions. The views on the rational use of natural and labor resources, especially in rural areas, were very relevant. Including:

- The rural population in the valley is projected to increase in the coming years, as natural growth was five times higher than in Russia and three times higher than in the CIS at that time;
- There is a growing need to address the problem of seasonal employment in rural areas, to attract the rural population to other sectors of production during the winter months;
- Development of agricultural labor sectors (horticulture, vegetable growing, horticulture, viticulture) and agricultural processing industries to solve the problem of employment in rural areas of the Fergana Valley;
- It is proposed to develop Central Fergana, as well as hills and foothills, taking into account the rate of population growth.

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All of the above proposals are not sufficiently sound if they are evaluated in terms of market economy and ecological balance. But the main problem inherent in the rural areas of the valley is to achieve a balance between natural and labor resources. The economic geographical study of rural areas focuses on assessing and forecasting the use of natural conditions and resources in the national economy (Nigmatov A., 2005). A landscape approach to the study of the nature of rural areas allows for the simultaneous study of orographic location, climate, hydrological and soil and biological resource indicators, and the assessment and prediction of natural agrarian potential.

The study of the rate of change of natural landscape indicators in rural areas, pollution and the ability of natural resources to regenerate themselves formed the basis of geographical research in the field of geoecology.

The geographical study of agriculture is carried out in two directions, in three stages. Socio-economic and geo-ecological aspects of the material organization of industries, especially the territorial organization and development of agriculture, are studied in detail. Also, the territorial organization, formation and development of industry, construction and transport networks in rural areas will be studied from the geo-ecological point of view.

In the second direction, aspects related to intangible industries (services, organization of research in rural areas and education, health, nature protection) are studied. Today in rural areas it is important to rationally locate research institutes, laboratories, experimental stations, vocational colleges, higher education institutions

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that serve the population and the economy, their needs. In this regard, one of the important tasks is the geo-ecological and economic analysis of the territorial aspects of the location of professional colleges and higher education institutions in rural areas in the field of agriculture, land reclamation and irrigation, agronomy, agro-economics.

Rural population geography is evolving as one of the traditional branches of population geography and demography. The socio-economic and environmental aspects of indicators such as rural population growth, location, labor resources and their employment in the agricultural sector will be studied. The study analyzes changes in the regional aspects of indicators such as the increase in the number and density of the rural population in the study area, the amount of land per capita and its change.

In current geographical research, environmental and geographical problems also play a leading role in the study of rural areas. At the heart of this research is the interaction of economy and population with nature, the regulation of anthropogenic impact on nature, the degree of resistance of nature to anthropogenic impacts, the geographical aspects of environmental problems in rural areas.

As a result, the level of geo-ecological and economic stress in the region, agro-demographic pressure and changes in the natural composition of the landscape will be normalized. A “landscape program” to improve the geo-ecological and economic situation in rural areas has been proposed, which identifies villages with separate “sustainable” development points, which maintain the geo-ecological and economic balance in the region and allow the use of landscape-friendly methods. .

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